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Short-run and Long-run Causality between Infrastructural Development and Economic Growth in India: A Panel ARDL Approach

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Abstract

Growth literature on infrastructure-driven development spectrum unanimously recognizes the positive relationship between infrastructural development and economic growth especially in developing countries. However, many countries still failed to recognize the importance of enhanced infrastructure in economic growth and these nations often find themselves into a confounded situation of resource constraints at one hand and too many developmental targets at other hand. Based on this background, the present paper wants to determine the impact of infrastructural development on economic growth using panel ARDL model of 29 states in India during 2007-2017 divulging the short-run and long-run dynamics of this inter-linkage. Subsequently, the study reveals that road and power infrastructure positively affects economic growth both in the long-run and short-run. In contrast, the results also show that there is no long-run relationship between railway and economic growth. Thus, the findings empirically reaffirmed the popular Hirschman's argument of development via excess capacity indicating the viability of attaining economic growth induced by infrastructural development as far as road and power infrastructure concerned.

Keywords: 1.Economic Growth, 2.Infrastructure, 3.Short-run and 4.Long-run Causality, 5.Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL).

I. Introduction

Growth literature on the infrastructure-led development spectrum, unanimously recognize the positive relationship between infrastructural development and economic growth especially in developing countries (Rostow, 1965; Rodenstein-Rodan, 1943; Nurkse, 1955; Leibenstein, 1957; Hirschman (1958). Most of the contemporary empirical studies also shares similar views on the significant role of public investment on infrastructural development particularly on railway, road and power sector providing important impetus on the path of rapid economic growth (Easterly and Rebelo, 1993; Songco, 2002; Majumdar, 2008; Pradhanand Bagchi, 2013).

According to World Bank, infrastructure functions like the wheel of the growth engine (World Development Report, 1994). A well-established network of infrastructural facilities accelerates economic growth by reducing transportation cost and opening new opportunities through better market access which in turn merges the primary sectors with the secondary sector in an economy, thus bringing the initial economic setup of potential industrialization especially in the developing countries where agriculture is predominant. It also indirectly alleviates poverty and improves standard of living. Hence, the role of public investment creating new and improved infrastructural facilities is one the main developmental strategies of economic acceleration in the developing countries.

Using both longitudinal dataset of 28 developed countries, Easterly and Rebelo (1993) have shown a very high correlation coefficient between economic growth and investment in transport and communication. Similarly, Baffes and Shah (1992) has revealed that public capital particularly infrastructural facilities and human resource development positively affects the per capita GDP of a nation using time series dataset of 25 developing as well as developed countries. Moreover, Ocampo et al. (2007) underlines the importance

of adequate infrastructure as a precondition for firms to be productive in an economy. Hence, this study emphasizes on the necessity of underdeveloped countries to create a threshold level of infrastructure to be productive and be able to attract private investments.

In developing countries, agriculture is the backbone of their economy and hence, most of their economic activities rely on and around the level of growth of the agricultural sector. Thus, economic development without proper improvement of the agriculture sector is highly in doubt. But the creation of new infrastructure facilities like road connectivity and electricity supply particularly in the rural areas gives a big push to the agrarian economy. Antle (1983) has empirically proved that the contribution of infrastructural facilities in agricultural productivity is significantly positive in both developing and developed countries taking a sample of both for developing countries alone and a mixed sample of developed and developing countries. Besides, the study by Dubey (2009) argues that development of states of Haryana and Punjab from northern India are due to their initial public investment on irrigation and infrastructural development has raised the productivity of the agricultural sector increasing the incomes of the general masses and hence, created a booming consumer market which in turn reduced the level of incidence of poverty.

Hence, the role of public investment on physical infrastructure is considered being one of the major preconditions for stimulating private investment and regional development (Rao, 1979). Investment in infrastructure crowded in private investment so that aggregate investment exceeded domestic savings to a larger extent (Srinivasan, 2003). But the variability of public investment particularly on infrastructure development in regional level in developing countries like India is one of the prime reasons of growing regional disparity. A study by Greene and Villanueva (1991) found that the level of private sector investment is a positive function of the trend level of public investment particularly in infrastructure. But, the public investment for provision of infrastructure is very inadequate in developing countries because of their resource constraints at one hand and need of many developmental targets to accomplish at other the hand. But private investment can complement public investment in resource scarce countries for higher economic growth. An empirical study shows that the adequate level of infrastructural facilities will increase standing of the economy to attract private investments (Ocampo et al., 2007). Hence, countries often need to build a threshold or minimum level of infrastructure to bring private investment into the economic system which in turn will lead further development of the economy.

Rapid industrialization, on the other hand, is important determinants of economic growth especially in developing and LDCs and good quality infrastructure works as catalyst of speedy industrialization. Conversely, the problem of infrastructure bottleneck in those countries impedes the growth process. Many studies argue that the infrastructural facilities have a very high degree of correlation with the extent of industrialization of a region (Dholakia, 2009). Infrastructure leads to higher productivity of different factors of production and hence, negligence of infrastructural development leads to a lower productivity of the other production factors (Rietveld and Nijkamp, 1992). In addition, the decisive tendency of selecting industrial location primarily depends on the high concentration of infrastructure of the region and availability of productive manpower which is generally found in cities and towns (Nath, 1971). Similarly, Deichmann et al., (2008) found that determination of industrial location in lagging regions especially in developing countries depends on the surplus benefits of infrastructure investments.

Moreover, a comparative statement of development indicators of developed and developing countries over time reveals the fact that a very high GDP (gross domestic product) and PCI (per capita income) are the indicators of the developed economy and steady rising GDP and PCI are the signs of developing countries. Under these circumstances, many studies show that the improvement of infrastructural services positively affects GDP and PCI. A study by Looney and Fredericksen (1981) argues that infrastructure has important effect on GDP and different regions (advanced and backward) show different responsiveness towards economic and social infrastructure. A World Bank study by Songco (2002) revealed the fact more technically and precisely that a 1 percent increase in the stock of infrastructure is associated with 1 percent increase in GDP across all country. Exchanging similar viewpoints Deichmann et

al. (2002) showed that a 10 percent increase in market access through infrastructure development leads to a 6 percent increases in labor productivity in Mexico. Similar findings in the Indian context by many empirical studies suggested that there is a positive interrelationship between the level of per capita income and infrastructure development (Shah, 1970; Majumdar, 2008; Pradhan and Bagchi, 2013).

However, many developing countries still failed to recognize the importance of public infrastructure in economic growth and often find themselves into a confounded situation of resource constraints at one hand and too many developmental targets at other hand. But, policy makers cannot deny the importance of other vital factors of economic development like education and health. Hence, without precise and clear knowledge of how infrastructural development affects economic growth, the policy makers may confront a perplexed situation where precedence of choice for budgetary allocation of public resources between different sectors of development. Thus, based on the above theoretical underpinning and empirical strengths, the present paper wants to measure the impact of infrastructural development on economic growth especially under the influences of short-run and long-run dynamics of the causal interlinkage between them among all Indian states over the period 2007-2017.

II. Sources of Data

The paper is mainly based on secondary data which are collected from various government sources and agencies over the time period 2005 to 2015 and across 29 Indian states excluding the union territories. Availabilities of infrastructures among the different states in the country are collected from Annual Reports of Indian Railways, Basic Road Statistics of India (Ministry of Road, Transport and Highways, Govt. of India) and Infrastructure Series of Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE, Mumbai). The GDP per capita (at constant price) across the states has been collected from Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

III. Methodology

Based on the technical suitability of the panel dataset, the paper employs the panel ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model to investigate the presence of causality between infrastructure and economic growth. Moreover, it also determines the exact impact of infrastructural development on economic growth in the long-run. This model is initially propounded by the duo Pesaran and Pesaran (1997) and later developed by the trio Pesaran-Shin-Smith (2000&2001). The popularity of the ARDL model actually relies on its applicability in case of small sample. According to Pesaran and Shin (1999) it allows whether the underlying variables is integrated of order zero or one [I(0) or I(1)]. Moreover, it also allows uneven lags for different variables in the model. Another advantage of ARDL model is that it takes the issue of endogeneity under consideration because the lags of both dependent and independent variables are included in this model (Pesaran et al, 1999; Samargandi et al, 2013). Besides, ARDL models provide both short-run as well as long-run causality which is very important while investigating causal relationship among variables in case of time series and panel data. ARDL model also provides the speed of adjustment like VECM model which gives us information about the adjustability of model in presence of sudden shocks among the variables in the long run and their self-correction of equilibrium at the rate of the coefficient of error correction term.

However, other panel models like pooled OLS panel model, fixed effects model (FEM) and random effects model (REM) have many technical pitfalls. Most of these models are having at least some kind of restrictions like either having common intercept or having common slope of the independent variables or having both. That is why these models do not take consideration of the consequences of regional heterogeneity (Samargandi et al, 2013). In FEM models this problem solved using dummy variables to capture the regional heterogeneity like individual intercept and slope of the independent variables but this method also leads to huge loss of degree of freedom (Baltagi, 2005). Moreover, the result of FEM model is biased in presence of endogeneity of variables and if the independent variables are correlated with the error term. Thus, the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of different regional variations cannot be captured by static panel models mentioned above. Hence, dynamic panel regression such as panel

autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model can be used to capture the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of the regions or states (Pesaran et al., 1999).

Thus, based on the above discussion, the following panel ARDL (p, q) model has been employed to determine the short-run as well as long-run causality between physical infrastructure (like railway, road, and power) and economic growth.

$$\Delta \text{Ln}(Y)_{it} = \theta_1 + \delta_1 \text{Ln}(Y)_{i(t-1)} + \delta_2 \text{Ln}(X)_{i(t-1)} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \alpha_{ij} \Delta \text{Ln}(Y)_{i(t-j)} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \beta_{ij} \Delta \text{Ln}(X)_{i(t-j)} + \varphi_{t-1} + \mu_{it}$$

Where,

Y_t is the dependent variable (in this model it is PCY)

But X_t here indicates a set of independent variables. In this model $X_t(s)$ are RAIL, ROAD and POWER.

$\alpha(s)$ are long-run coefficients and

δ is the coefficient of error correction term (ECT)

$\alpha(s)$ and $\beta(s)$ are short-run coefficients of lagged dependent variables and independent variables respectively.

p & q are lag of dependent and independent variables respectively and

μ_{it} is the error term.

IV. Results and Discussion

Table 1 displays the level of infrastructure development in railway, road and power consumption (power generation plus imports from other agencies) in India over the period 1990-2015. The statistics indicates that the growth of railway infrastructure was very sluggish whereas road and power showed a very high annual growth compared to the 1990 level in the country.

Table 1: Level of Infrastructural Development in India (Availability per 100 sq. km)

Year	Railway Route (km)	Road Length (km)	Power Consumption (kWh)
1990	2.10	67.3	8.3
2000	2.11	111.9	15.9
2010	2.17	157.8	27.2
2015	2.18	176.0	39.7
CAGR	0.2%	4.1%	7.0%

Source: Author's calculation based on the secondary data.

However, this occurrence of tremendous growth of road and power infrastructure as shown in the Table 1 has any significant contributions to economic growth in India, though a matter of tricky question. To investigate this fact that how the infrastructural development affects economic growth, hence, is the main aim of the paper. Since the paper employs panel dataset for ARDL model for the analysis, it is customary to check for panel unit roots of the variables to identify whether the variables are stationary or nonstationary at level and at various differences of the particularly variables. However, it not necessary to test unit roots because the ARDL model feeds both nonstationary as well as stationary variable.

Table 2: Summary Statistics of the Panels

Variable		Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Observations
PCY	overall	11.05	0.55	9.43	12.54	N = 319
	between		0.52	9.86	12.27	n = 29
	within		0.20	10.42	11.83	T = 11
RAILWAY	overall	5.93	3.01	0	9.10	N = 319
	between		3.02	0	8.67	n = 29
	within		0.46	3.88	8.00	T = 11
ROAD	overall	11.10	1.30	7.54	13.32	N = 319
	between		1.30	8.24	12.80	n = 29
	within		0.22	10.39	11.77	T = 11
POWER	overall	9.14	1.86	5.32	11.86	N = 319
	between		1.87	5.76	11.59	n = 29
	within		0.23	8.49	9.87	T = 11

Source: Author's Calculations.

Table 3 displays the output of one of the most frequently used panel unit root tests, i.e. *Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS)* test. The results of the test confirm that the variables are nonstationary in their levels but found to be stationary at first difference except railway. Hence, our panel dataset is a combination of stationary as well as nonstationary variables, which in other words also recognized as integrated of order zero and one respectively. Hence there are no technical restrictions of applying the panel ARDL (p, q) model.

Table 3: Results of Panel Unit Root (Im, Pesaran and Shin Test) Tests

Variables	Series	Statistic	Inference
PCY	Level	2.482	Nonstationary
RAILWAY	Level	-1.561**	Stationary
ROAD	Level	6.273	Nonstationary
POWER	Level	5.566	Nonstationary
PCY	1st Difference	-3.163*	Stationary
RAIL	1st Difference	0.873*	Stationary
ROAD	1st Difference	-2.930***	Stationary
POWER	1st Difference	-1.188**	Stationary

Source: Author's calculations.
Note: *** Significant at 1 percent level. ** Significant at 5 percent level.
* Significant at 10 percent level.

Subsequently, Table 4 displays the results of panel ARDL model which includes both the coefficients of short-run as well as long-run causality. Additionally, the same table shows three different estimators of panel ARDL model, i.e. PMG (Pooled Mean Group), MG (Mean Group) and DFE (Dynamic Fixed Effects) along with Hausman specification tests which is used to examine the comparative efficiency and consistency among the three estimators. For this purpose, two different Hausman tests have been carried out among the estimators viz. Between PMG and MG and Between PMG and DFE. The Hausman test indicates that the DFE is the best and efficient estimator among them. All these three estimators employ the Maximum Likelihood (ML) method.

The Hausman tests among PMG, MG and DFE estimators of the panel ARDL model statistically validate that the DFE estimator is the most efficient among them. The output of the DFE estimator (Table 4) reveals that the road and power infrastructure positively affect economic growth measured in terms of per capita GDP both at the long-run and short-run. The statistically significant coefficient of road is 0.404 which implies that a 1 unit increase in the size of road will lead to 0.40 unit increase in PCY in the long-run. Similarly, 1 unit increase in the availability of power will lead to 0.49 unit rise in PCY in the long-run. But the results also indicate that there is no long-run relationship between railway and PCY.

Table 4: Results of Panel ARDL (1, 1, 1, 1) Model

Model Specification: PCY= f (RAIL, ROAD & POWER)						
Variables	Pooled Mean Group (PMG) Estimator		Mean Group (MG) Estimator		Dynamic Fixed Effect (DFE) Estimator	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Long-run Coefficients						
RAIL	0.126***	0.029	-8.554	7.065	0.042	0.035
ROAD	0.894***	0.131	-.358	0.632	0.404***	0.113
POWER	0.989***	0.051	1.383	1.874	0.492***	0.108
Short-run Coefficients						
ΔRAIL	-7.087	0.032	-3.213	2.576	0.006	0.011
ΔROAD	0.103**	6.392	0.154**	0.078	0.123***	0.030
ΔPOWER	0.046	0.049	0.193**	0.088	0.102**	0.046
Intercept	0.701**	0.056	-31.553	33.923	-0.339	0.213
ECT	-0.073**	0.311	0.422**	0.195	-0.213***	0.037
Hausman test between PMG and MG (h-test) = -14.01 (p>0.10)						
Hausman test between PMG and DFE (h-test) = 33.9*** (p<0.01)						
Inference = Dynamic Fixed Effect (DFE) is the efficient estimator among them.						
Source: Author's calculations.						
Note: *** Significant at 1 percent level. ** Significant at 5 percent level. * Significant at 10 percent level.						

Moreover, the statistically significant short-run coefficients also demonstrate the fact that in response to any external shock or disequilibrium of the previous year will be corrected among themselves in the current year to maintain the long-run relationship. However, the coefficient of error correction term (ECT) is negatively signed and statistically significant which is the indication of the fact that the model is stable in the long-run. In addition, it also speaks about the speed of adjustment back to the long-run equilibrium in response to any external shock in the short-run. Thus, the coefficient of -0.213, in our model, indicates that 21.3 percent of the disequilibrium in the previous year will be corrected in the current year to maintain the long-run equilibrium relationship among road, power and economic growth.

V. Conclusion

To summarize, the study successfully investigated and measured the short-run and long-run impact of infrastructural development on economic growth in Indian context employing panel dataset of 29 states over the period 2007-2017. The findings reveal that infrastructure particularly the availability of road and power positively affects economic growth both in the short-run and long-run with a high beta coefficient emphasising the empirical validity of the Hirschman's argument of *development via excess capacity* indicating the viability of attaining economic growth induced by infrastructural augmentation especially in road and power sector. Though, the railway infrastructure has not shown any causal interactions with economic growth in the country but it does not mean that railway is no longer important for economic acceleration. Thus, the finding of the present paper provides an empirical reinforcement for the policy

makers suggesting greater importance initially to the development of road and power infrastructure in India, where the necessity of well-established network of road communication and round-the-clock power services for the rapid industrialization is the need of the hour.

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